

SECONDARY STRUCTURE EFFECTS ON THE PROCESS-INDUCED RESIDUAL STRESS DEVELOPMENT OF CYLINDER STRUCTURE

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SUMMARY: In this paper the viscoelastic analysis on the process-induced residual stresses of cylindrical structure by filament winding process is presented. The focus was on the effects of the secondary structures such as teflon tape and mandrel on the final residual stress. The material used in this study was Hercules AS4/3501-6 prepreg system. The material behavior of 3501-6 epoxy during cure was modeled by a series of stress relaxation tests for the viscoelastic constitutive equations of the composite during cure. A finite element method was used to calculate the residual stresses, and the results at the selected time during cure cycle are shown to understand the mechanism of stress development. It was found that small final residual stresses are developed when the material with high Young's modulus and thermal expansion coefficient is used for the mandrel structure .

KEYWORDS: filament winding, thermoset composites processing, residual stresses, viscoelasticity, stress relaxation

INTRODUCTION

The stress free states at cure temperature has been widely assumed for the process-induced residual stress analyses of polymer matrix fiber-reinforced composite structures. Figure 1 shows dynamic mechanical analysis on fully cured Hercules AS4/3501-6 composite. In this Figure, the glass transition temperature of fully cured specimen is 213°C. Reflecting the fact that the cure temperature of this material is 177°C, it is questionable that full stress relaxation of the residual stress occurs at the cure temperature. Recent studies on the viscoelastic residual stress analyses of AS4/3501-6 laminated plates [1-5] showed that the temperature-degree of cure-dependent relaxation behavior as well as the resin shrinkage during cure had a great influence on the final residual stress development. In the case of cylindrical structures manufactured by filament winding, the interaction between the mandrel and the composite structure makes the residual stress development problem much more complex.

The filament winding process is commonly composed of the three steps: 1) winding the composite tows onto a mandrel structure, 2) curing, 3) cooldown and removing the mandrel. After winding, the composite and the mandrel structure is placed in an oven or autoclave to cure the composite structure. The cure processing is very similar to the laminate case except for the additional constraints due to the mandrel structure. Numerous studies have examined process-induced residual stresses of cylindrical structures [6-14]. However, their solutions

were based on the elastic approach. When the entire cure cycle was considered, assumption of either a simple linear relationship between degree of cure and the mechanical properties of composite [11,12], or a step function to describe the increase in composite material properties after gelation was taken [13,14]. For the case of cylindrical structures, apparently no viscoelastic analysis of process-induced residual stresses including the mandrel effect has been attempted.

In this study viscoelastic process-induced residual stresses in cylindrical composite structures are analyzed. The thermorheologically complex model for AS4/3501-6 prepreg system developed in the previous works [1-5] was used for the constitutive equation. The residual stress development of the cross-ply cylinder structure by autoclave cure process was investigated. The slip effect of teflon film between mandrel and composite structure was taken into account. Young's modulus and the thermal expansion coefficient were changed to examine the mandrel property effect. The results were compared to each other to find the condition for small final residual stresses in the composite structure.

During consolidation fibers move inward in the radial direction and resin percolates outward. There is a loss of fiber tension as this process occurs. In the following analysis the effect of winding tension is assumed to be negligible.

VISCOELASTIC CONSTITUTIVE EQUATION

In the previous study [1,4], the most general expression for the constitutive relationship of an anisotropic viscoelastic material during cure in matrix form was presented such that

$$\sigma_i(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t Q_{ij}(t, \tau) \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} (\epsilon_j(\tau) - \tilde{\epsilon}_j(\tau)) d\tau \quad (1)$$

Here, σ_i is the stresses and ϵ_j and $\tilde{\epsilon}_j$ are total strains and non-mechanical strains, respectively. The present and past times are t and τ , respectively. The time dependent effects in the stiffness matrix Q_{ij} can be temperature, moisture, degree of cure and all other factors which have influence on the material property during cure. If the cure process is spatial dependent, Q_{ij} is also a function of location.

The non-mechanical strains $\tilde{\epsilon}_j$ in the polymer matrix composite cure process can be described as

$$\tilde{\epsilon}_j(\tau) = \phi_j(\alpha, T, M) \Delta T(t) + \beta_j(\alpha, T, M) \Delta M(t) + \gamma_j(\alpha, T, M) \Delta \alpha(t) \quad (2)$$

ϕ_j = effective thermal expansion coeff.

β_j = effective moisture expansion coeff.

γ_j = effective chemical expansion coeff.

ΔT = change in temperature

ΔM = change in moisture concentration

$\Delta \alpha$ = change in degree of cure

Equation (1) can be simplified to time-superposition integration form if the material shows thermorheologically simple behavior to temperature and moisture at a constant degree of cure α_c . With this assumption and if there is no strain history before $t=0$, equation (1) can be rewritten as anisotropic linear viscoelastic constitutive equation such that

$$\sigma_i(t) = \int_0^t Q_{ij}(\alpha_c, \xi - \xi') \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} (\varepsilon_j(\tau) - \tilde{\varepsilon}_j(\tau)) d\tau \quad (3)$$

where,

$$\xi = \int_0^t \chi[\alpha_c, T(s), M(s)] ds \quad (4)$$

$$\xi' = \int_0^\tau \chi[\alpha_c, T(s), M(s)] ds \quad (5)$$

In equations (4) and (5), χ is the shift function and is a function of degree of cure, temperature and moisture, and s is the time integration variable. This research is based on equation (3), which implies that the material is assumed to be thermorheologically simple at constant degree of cure.

For simplicity, the following notation is adopted such that

The caret on the variables signifies the principal axes condition. The principal axes r , θ and l of the cylinder are shown in Figure 2. If the cylinder structure is axisymmetric and each layer is transversely isotropic, equation (6) is expressed as the matrix form such that

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \hat{\sigma}_l \\ \hat{\sigma}_\theta \\ \hat{\sigma}_r \\ \hat{\sigma}_{l\theta} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{Q}_{11} & \hat{Q}_{12} & \hat{Q}_{12} & 0 \\ \hat{Q}_{12} & \hat{Q}_{22} & \hat{Q}_{23} & 0 \\ \hat{Q}_{12} & \hat{Q}_{23} & \hat{Q}_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \hat{Q}_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \hat{\varepsilon}_l \\ \hat{\varepsilon}_\theta \\ \hat{\varepsilon}_r \\ \hat{\varepsilon}_{l\theta} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{Q}_{11} &= \frac{1 - \nu_{r\theta} \nu_{\theta r}}{\Lambda} \hat{E}_l \\ \hat{Q}_{12} &= \frac{\nu_{lr} + \nu_{rl} \nu_{r\theta}}{\Lambda} \hat{E}_l \\ \hat{Q}_{22} &= \frac{1 - \nu_{rl} \nu_{lr}}{\Lambda} \hat{E}_\theta \\ \hat{Q}_{23} &= \frac{\nu_{r\theta} + \nu_{l\theta} \nu_{rl}}{\Lambda} \hat{E}_\theta \\ \hat{Q}_{44} &= \hat{G}_{12} = \hat{G}_{13} \\ \Lambda &= 1 - \nu_{rl} \nu_{lr} - \nu_{l\theta} \nu_{\theta l} - \nu_{r\theta} \nu_{\theta r} - 2\nu_{l\theta}^2 \nu_{r\theta} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Therefore, the independent time-dependent engineering properties are

$$\hat{E}_l, \hat{E}_\theta = \hat{E}_r, \nu_{l\theta} = \nu_{lr}, \nu_{\theta r}, \hat{G}_{l\theta} = \hat{G}_{rl} \quad (10)$$

In the previous studies [1,3,4], the stress relaxation behavior of 3501-6 epoxy resin system during cure was modeled in a thermorheologically complex manner by a series of stress relaxation tests. On the basis of this model the stress relaxation model of AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite was developed. For AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite, it was assumed that the material behavior was thermorheologically simple at constant degree of cure,

and the effective time-dependent stiffnesses were modeled using a series of exponential function such that

$$\hat{Q}_{ij}(\alpha, \xi) = \hat{Q}_{ij}^{\infty} + \sum_{\omega=1}^N \hat{Q}_{ij}^{\omega} \exp\left(-\frac{\xi(\alpha, T)}{\eta_{\omega}(\alpha)}\right) \quad (11)$$

where $\hat{Q}_{ij}^{\omega} = \hat{Q}_{ij}^u - \hat{Q}_{ij}^{\infty}$ and \hat{Q}_{ij}^u is elastic stiffness and \hat{Q}_{ij}^{∞} is equilibrium stiffness. η is discrete relaxation time, and is a function of degree of cure. The reduced parameter ξ was modeled as a function of degree of cure as well as temperature. The layer was assumed as transversely isotropic, and the four independent elastic stiffness are listed in Table 1. Each stiffness was modeled by ten term exponential series, and the equilibrium stiffness was calculated using partition factor $R = 1/7$ based on the stress relaxation test result of fully cured AS4/3501-6 composite [1]. Since the properties in the fiber direction are essentially time-independent, \hat{Q}_{11} and \hat{Q}_{12} in Table 1 were assumed to be constant. The remaining stiffnesses were assumed to relax according to the same shift function.

FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

In previous works [3,4], a finite element model was developed for the AS4/3501-6 laminate cases. Similar formulation was used in the cylinder structure case .

A recursive formulation presented by Taylor et al. [15] was applied to account for the degree of cure effect as well as to overcome large memory storage problem in solving the time superposition integration equation (3). To adopt the method, the derivative of the global displacement and the thermal-chemical strains were assumed to be piecewise linear during each time interval. Additionally, the degree of cure α is assumed constant during each time interval so that

Table 1: Elastic stiffness, thermal and chemical expansion coefficient of fully cure AS4/3501-6 cylinder in the principal directions

Q_{11} (GPa)	127.4
Q_{12} (GPa)	3.88
Q_{22} (GPa)	10.0
Q_{44} (GPa)	2.57
ϕ_i ($\mu\epsilon/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	0.5
$\phi_r = \phi_{\theta}$ ($\mu\epsilon/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	35.3
γ_i ($\mu\epsilon$)	-167
$\gamma_r = \gamma_{\theta}$ ($\mu\epsilon$)	-8,810

Table 2: The material properties of aluminum, teflon film and steel

	E (GPa)	ν	ϕ ($\mu\epsilon/^{\circ}\text{C}$)
Aluminum	72.4	0.3	23.6
Steel	200	0.3	11.3
Teflon Film	same with mandrel	0.3	same with mandrel

Here, $\alpha(\bar{t}_k)$ is obtained separately through thermo-chemical model of the composite. The detailed formulation is presented in reference [1].

Since the cylinder structure is assumed to be axisymmetric, the strains in this case are calculated from

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_r &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \\ \varepsilon_l &= \frac{\partial w}{\partial l} \\ \varepsilon_\theta &= \frac{u}{r} \\ \varepsilon_{rl} &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial l} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial r}\end{aligned}\quad (13).$$

To consider the mandrel effect, the elastic response of the mandrel material must be combined with the composite structure. In addition, a thin teflon film is used to separate the composite structure and mandrel after cure. Since the film material allows slip to occur in the l -direction, a stress discontinuity is introduced in this direction. Slip elements were inserted between the mandrel and composite structure to simulate the effects of the film.

The mandrel and film materials are assumed to be composed of elastic materials with the constitutive equations such as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_l \\ \sigma_\theta \\ \sigma_r \\ \sigma_{lr} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} & d_{13} & 0 \\ d_{12} & d_{22} & d_{23} & 0 \\ d_{13} & d_{23} & d_{33} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & d_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_l \\ \varepsilon_\theta \\ \varepsilon_r \\ \varepsilon_{lr} \end{Bmatrix}\quad (14).$$

The stiffnesses are expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}d_{11} = d_{22} = d_{33} &= \frac{E(1-\nu)}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} = d_1 \\ d_{12} = d_{13} = d_{23} &= \frac{E\nu}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} = d_2 \\ d_{44} &= \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)} = d_3\end{aligned}\quad (15)$$

where E and ν are Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, respectively. All properties of mandrel and teflon film were assumed to be constant throughout the cure cycle. A thin teflon film covers the surface of the mandrel and this film, in general, is viscoelastic. However, since the thickness of the teflon in r -direction is negligible compared to the mandrel, the stress relaxation behavior of the teflon can be neglected. Additionally, the thermal expansion coefficient of the teflon is assumed to be same as that of the mandrel material. In the analysis, only d_{33} in equation (14) is given a non-zero value for the teflon elements. All the material properties used in the finite element analysis for the mandrel and teflon film are listed in Table 2. Whenever the radial stress at the interface between the composite cylinder and the

mandrel structure became tensile ($\sigma_r \geq 0$), the value of d_{33} was reduced to 10^{-9} GPa in order to simulate the separation effect between the mandrel and cylinder.

In this analysis, the moisture effect is neglected and the effective thermal and chemical expansion coefficients are assumed to be constant during cure. The effective thermal expansion coefficients for the composite cylinder are listed in Table 1.

To consider the chemical shrinkage effect, the volume shrinkage is modeled by a linear expression as

$$V_{ch}(\alpha) = V_{ch}^T \alpha \quad (16)$$

where V_{ch}^T is total volumetric shrinkage of the resin. A typical value of 5% for V_{ch}^T for epoxy was assumed for the chemical shrinkage strain. The corresponding effective chemical shrinkage coefficients are calculated by a self-consistent micromechanical model [16], and they are listed in Table 1.

In the reference [1], the effect of the cure dependent equilibrium modulus was studied for thin laminate cases. It was found that the cure dependency of the equilibrium stiffness did not have significant effect on the final residual stress. Therefore, it was assumed that the equilibrium stiffnesses were constant during cure in this study.

NUMERICAL STUDIES

In the results which follow the stacking sequence for the cylinder structure in Figure 2 was $[mandrel/teflon\ film/0^\circ/90^\circ]_T$. The thickness of the mandrel structure (mandrel and teflon) was chosen to be equal to 1/3 of the total cylinder structure thickness. In this case $h=3h_m$. The thickness of the teflon film was 1% of the mandrel structure thickness. The structural geometry considered is a thickness to mean diameter ratio of $r_c/b=13$ with an aspect ratio a/b of 3. Due to the symmetry of the cylinder structure, only a quarter of the section was analyzed, and the following results are at $l=0$.

Figure 3 shows the temperature cycle and corresponding degree of cure history for the MRC cycle. The temperature of the first dwell is 116°C for one hour. In the second dwell, the temperature is 177°C for 2 hours. $2.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ was equally applied to the increase and the decrease rate of the temperature of the cure cycle. With this temperature cycle, degree of cure advancement was calculated on the basis of the thermo-chemical cure kinetic models for AS4/3501-6 composite in the references [17]. It was assumed that the temperature and degree of cure are changed uniformly through the thickness of the composite structure during cure. The corresponding stress distributions are shown at nine specific times (37, 96, 121, 181, 240, 256, 274, 290 and 302 minutes) throughout the cure cycle in the figures which follow. These times are overlaid on the cure cycle in Figure 3.

Figures 4-9 represent the stress developments during cure cycle. In this case the mandrel material is aluminum. Figures 4 and 5 show the radial stress profile developments during cure. To the start of cure temperature at 121 min, the stress distribution in the cylinder structure is compressive. During cure from 121 min to 181 min, the compressive stress is slightly changed due to the resin shrinkage effect. As the temperature is decreased during cooldown stage, the stress distribution is changed from compression to tension. After the

separation is occurred between the mandrel and the composite structure at about 46°C, the stress at the mandrel remains zero while the stress at the composite structure is tensile. The maximum stress after cooldown is found to be 1.17 MPa at the 0°/90° interface. The axial stress distributions are shown in Figures 6 and 7. Since the displacement discontinuity between the mandrel and the composite structure exists, there is no stress development in the mandrel. Immediately before cooldown the 0° layer is in compression and the 90° layer is in tension. After cooldown the stress magnitudes are all elevated significantly. The final axial stress at the inner radius is -35 MPa. The hoop stress distributions are shown in Figures 8 and 9. The stress distributions in the mandrel and 90° are significant in the magnitude due to the mandrel expansion at the cure temperature. After the mandrel is separated during cooldown, the final residual stress in 0° layer is tensile while the stress in 90° layer is compressive. It was found that the radial and hoop stress magnitudes during cure temperature are very large compared to the final residual stresses due to the mandrel expansion.

To investigate the influence of mandrel material properties on the final residual stress, the aluminum mandrel is changed to steel mandrel. The material properties are listed in Table 2. The stress profile developments during cure are similar to the previous cases. And only the final radial stresses are considered. Figure 10 shows the comparison of the final radial stress distributions for both cases under the same cure cycle in Figure 3. The maximum stress with steel mandrel shows slightly higher value. To investigate the material property effects further, three cases of Young's modulus of mandrel materials are compared in Figure 11. The thermal expansion coefficient was kept constant as $2.36\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$. The results show that the final radial stress is increased as Young's modulus decreases. To examine the thermal expansion coefficient effect, three different cases with constant Young's modulus of 72.4 GPa are compared in Figure 12. In this case, the final radial stress is increased as the thermal expansion coefficient is decreased.

CONCLUSION

In this research, the residual stress in the cylinder structure by cure process is analyzed. The stress profile developments during cure were presented to understand the stress development mechanism. The finite element method was used with axisymmetric assumption on the cylinder structure, and slip elements were inserted to simulate the slip effect and separation effect by teflon between the composite structure and mandrel. Parametric studies such as Young's modulus and thermal expansion coefficient of the mandrel on the final residual stresses were performed to investigate the effects of the mandrel material properties. It was found that the residual stresses at the cure temperature were very high in magnitude due to the thermal expansion of the mandrel compared to the final residual stress. And the usage of high Young's modulus and high thermal expansion coefficient of the mandrel material showed low final residual stresses in the case of AS4/3501-6 composite. In summary, the stress developments over full cure cycle with accurate information about material properties has to be analyzed to find the reason of damages of the composite structure by the residual stresses.

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Fig. 1: Storage and loss shear moduli versus temperature for fully cured [0]₁₀ AS4/3501-6 laminate

Fig. 3: Temperature and degree of cure history of AS4/3501-6 during MRC cycle

Fig. 2: Geometry of the cylinder structure.

Fig. 4: Radial stress distributions during cure of a [0/90]_T composite cylinder up to the start of cooldown. The mandrel material is aluminum.

Fig. 5: Radial stress distributions during cooldown of a [0/90]_T composite cylinder. The mandrel material is aluminum.

Fig. 6: Axial stress distributions during cure of a $[0/90]_T$ composite cylinder up to the start of cooldown.

Fig. 10: Final residual stress in the radial direction using aluminum and steel mandrels

Fig. 7: Axial stress distribution during cooldown of a $[0/90]_T$ composite cylinder.

Fig. 11: Comparison of final radial stresses using different mandrel structures. The thermal expansion coefficient is kept constant as $2.36 \mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$ for all cases.

Fig. 8: Hoop stress distributions during cure of a $[0/90]_T$ composite cylinder up to the start of cooldown.

Fig. 12: Comparison of final radial stresses using different mandrel structures. The Young's modulus is kept constant as 72.4 GPa for all cases.

Fig. 9: Hoop stress distributions during cooldown of a $[0/90]_T$ composite cylinder.